

A POD-based Reduced-order Model and Entropy-driven Weight Window Acceleration Method in the RMC Code

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ABSTRACT

This work constructs a POD-based Reduced-Order Model (POD-ROM) in the RMC Monte Carlo code and proposes a SHannon-Entropy-based Weight-window method (SHEW) for efficient solution of deep-penetration ex-vessel shielding problems in pressurized water reactors. A one-dimensional RPV ex-vessel shielding configuration derived from the PCA benchmark is used as the comparing case. High-fidelity RMC flux snapshots are generated under perturbed geometric and material conditions and used to build a physics-constrained POD-ROM. The results show that the ROM reproduces the radial fast-neutron flux with R^2 close to 1.0, RMSE on the order of 10^{-3} , and an overall mean relative error of about 5 %, while reducing the computational time by 5–6 orders of magnitude compared with full RMC simulations. The POD-ROM is further employed to rapidly analyse response distributions under localized perturbations and to construct importance measures based on Shannon entropy and Kullback-Leibler divergence, from which SHEW automatically generates a continuous radial distribution of mesh weight-window lower bounds. When the resulting entropy-driven weight windows are embedded into RMC and compared with a traditional power-law cell-importance scheme, the results for a cavity tally outside the RPV indicate that SHEW maintains good agreement with high-precision reference fluxes, increases the figure-of-merit by approximately one order of magnitude, and significantly improves sampling efficiency in the deep-penetration region. Overall, the study demonstrates a physically interpretable weight-window quantification method and a rapid WW-setup procedure tailored to classical PWR ex-vessel shielding configurations.

Keywords: PWR ex-vessel shielding; RMC; POD-ROM; Shannon entropy; weight-window

1. INTRODUCTION

Fast-neutron fluence evaluation in the reactor pressure vessel (RPV) is critical for assessing embrittlement and structural integrity in pressurized water reactors (PWRs) [1]. Although full-scope Monte Carlo (MC) simulation is preferred for its high fidelity [2], ex-vessel shielding remains challenging because it is a deep-penetration problem with 4–6 orders of magnitude flux attenuation [3], which renders the computational cost prohibitive [4]. Consequently, developing automated variance reduction (VR) or weight-window (WW) optimization methods that avoid empirical tuning remains essential for practical engineering.

Current practices rely on the Consistent Adjoint Driven Importance Sampling (CADIS) [5] and the Method of Automatic Generation of Importances by Calculation (MAGIC) [6]. CADIS achieves efficiency through deterministic adjoint fluxes but suffers from mesh incompatibility and prior-calculation requirements. Conversely, MAGIC uses forward MC simulations but remains computationally expensive and sensitive to initial source bias in complex multi-layer systems.

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Furthermore, both methods lack a consistent, quantitative definition for WW lower bounds, often leading to user-dependent outcomes.

This study introduces a fast, physically interpretable WW quantification framework implemented in the RMC code [7]. A Proper Orthogonal Decomposition–based Reduced-Order Model (POD-ROM) [8] is developed to predict radial flux attenuation accurately. Subsequently, a new Shannon Entropy-based Weight-window (SHEW) method is proposed to automatically quantify WW lower bounds via entropy-increment mapping. This integrated approach provides an efficient solution for accelerating deep-penetration analyses in PWR shielding designs.

2. METHODOLOGY AND IMPLEMENTATION IN RMC CODE

2.1. POD-based Reduced-Order Model

A POD-based reduced-order model is developed to approximate the high-dimensional neutron flux field in a low-dimensional subspace. Let $\phi(x; p) \in \mathbb{R}^M$, where x denotes spatial mesh points and $p \in \mathbb{R}^d$ denotes perturbation parameters. For N sampled inputs $\{p_i\}_{i=1}^N$, the snapshot matrix is

$$\Phi = [\phi^{(1)}, \phi^{(2)}, \dots, \phi^{(N)}] \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times N} \quad (1)$$

POD seeks a rank- r ($r \ll M$) orthogonal subspace minimizing the snapshot projection error. Using singular value decomposition (SVD),

$$\Phi = U \Sigma V^T \quad (2)$$

where $U = [u_1, \dots, u_M]$ contains orthonormal modes. Retaining the first r modes yield the reduced basis $\psi_k(x) = u_k$ and the expansion

$$\phi(x; \mathbf{p}_i) \approx \sum_{k=1}^r a_k^{(i)} \psi_k(x) \quad (3)$$

This basis is optimal in the Euclidean norm by minimizing the total reconstruction error under orthonormality constraints:

$$\min_{\{\psi_k\}_{k=1}^r} \sum_{i=1}^N \left\| \phi^{(i)} - \sum_{k=1}^r \langle \phi^{(i)}, \psi_k \rangle \psi_k \right\|_2^2, \text{ s.t. } \langle \psi_k, \psi_l \rangle = \delta_{kl} \quad (4)$$

Purely data-driven POD modes may exhibit non-physical artifacts, such as negative values and spurious oscillations. To improve physical consistency, three 1-D transport/diffusion-informed penalties are imposed. For the steady state 1-D diffusion model

$$-D \frac{d^2 \phi(x)}{dx^2} + \Sigma_a(x) \phi(x) = S(x) \quad (5)$$

solutions are typically smooth away from boundaries and strong sources. Accordingly, a second-derivative smoothness penalty is introduced for each mode:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{diff}}^{(k)} = \left\| \frac{d^2 \psi_k}{dx^2} \right\|_2^2 \approx \left\| D_2 \psi_k \right\|_2^2 \quad (6)$$

To discourage negative flux components, a non-negativity penalty is added:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{neg}}^{(k)} = \sum_{j=1}^M \max(0, -\psi_k(x_j)) \quad (7)$$

To avoid sharp spatial discontinuities, a first-derivative (continuity) penalty is further applied:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{cont}}^{(k)} = \left\| \frac{d \psi_k}{dx} \right\|_2^2 \approx \left\| D_1 \psi_k \right\|_2^2 \quad (8)$$

Combining these terms gives the physics-constrained objective:

$$\min_{\{\psi_k\}_{k=1}^r} J = \sum_{i=1}^N \left\| \phi^{(i)} - \sum_{k=1}^r a_k^{(i)} \psi_k \right\|_2^2 + \lambda_1 \sum_{k=1}^r \mathcal{L}_{\text{diff}}^{(k)} + \lambda_2 \sum_{k=1}^r \mathcal{L}_{\text{neg}}^{(k)} + \lambda_3 \sum_{k=1}^r \mathcal{L}_{\text{cont}}^{(k)} \quad (9)$$

Here $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3$ control the strength of the physical constraints. This preserves POD's approximation efficiency while promoting transport-consistent modal behavior, providing a reliable surrogate for fast flux prediction and entropy-based evaluation in deep-penetration shielding.

2.2. SHEW Method

In deep-penetration shielding, local perturbations may substantially alter the distribution of tally responses. Metrics based only on mean/variance may miss distributional distortions, especially tail changes that dominate rare-event transport. SHEW therefore adopts information-theoretic measures to quantify regional importance by comparing response distributions before and after localized perturbations, and maps the resulting score to weight-window (WW) parameters.

For the reference state, let the response distribution be $f_{Y,0}(y)$ with Shannon entropy [9,10]:

$$H_0 = - \int f_{Y,0}(y) \ln f_{Y,0}(y) dy \quad (10)$$

After perturbing region Ω_r , the POD-ROM yields the perturbed distribution $f_{Y,r}(y)$ and entropy gain

$$\Delta H_r = H_r - H_0 \quad (11)$$

which reflects the uncertainty increase attributable to Ω_r . To further capture distribution shape differences (particularly tails), the Kullback-Leibler (KL) [11] divergence is introduced:

$$D_{KL,r} = \int f_{Y,r}(y) \ln \frac{f_{Y,r}(y)}{f_{Y,0}(y)} dy \quad (12)$$

A composite regional importance score is then defined as

$$I_r = \alpha \Delta H_r + (1 - \alpha) D_{KL,r}, \alpha \in [0,1] \quad (13)$$

To translate importance into WW lower bounds, an exponential mapping consistent with attenuation behavior is used:

$$W_{\min,r} = W_0 \exp(-\beta \tilde{I}_r) \quad (14)$$

where W_0 is a reference bound, $\beta > 0$ controls sensitivity, and \tilde{I}_r is the normalized score. For highly non-uniform importance fields, a power-law mapping can also be used:

$$W_{\min,r} = W_0 \tilde{I}_r^{-\gamma}, \gamma > 0 \quad (15)$$

Through these steps, SHEW converts distributional sensitivity into regional importance scores and then into radial WW bounds, which are applied in RMC to accelerate deep-penetration transport.

3. DEVELOPMENT AND CAPABILITY ANALYSIS OF THE 1-D POD-ROM MODEL

3.1. Data Preparation and Construction of the 1-D PWR Ex-vessel POD-ROM

A simplified 1-D shielding model was implemented in RMC to represent the radial ex-vessel configuration of a typical PWR RPV, based on the PCA benchmark [12]. The model retains only the radial transport dimension, applies reflective lateral boundary conditions, and uses a uniform ^{235}U Watt-spectrum source in the core region. As shown in Fig. 1, the geometry consists of concentric layers (water, aluminum, thermal shield, RPV steel, and concrete), exhibiting typical deep-penetration attenuation. All snapshots were generated with continuous-energy RMC transport to avoid multi-group approximation and preserve energy-dependent physics. Eleven perturbation parameters, including layer-interface locations and material densities, were selected and sampled using Latin hypercube sampling within the RAVEN-RMC workflow [13], as detailed in Table I. This process produced 1000 high-fidelity input-output snapshots.

Figure 1. Schematic of the 1-D PWR ex-vessel shielding model

The snapshots were then preprocessed for POD basis extraction. The 1-D steady-state diffusion equation (Eq. 5) is introduced only to define physics-based regularization terms during POD-basis optimization, enforcing smoothness and non-negativity of the reconstructed flux; it is not used as the governing solver and thus does not introduce diffusion-discretization bias. Finally, regression models are trained to map perturbation parameters to modal coefficients, yielding a POD-ROM that enables rapid and physically consistent reconstruction of the radial flux field.

Table I. Perturbation input parameters for the 1-D shielding model.

ID	Perturbation input parameter	Distribution range
1	Right surface position of aluminum plate (cm)	(U(6, 10))
2	Left surface position of thermal shield (cm)	(U(18, 22))
3	Right surface position of thermal shield (cm)	(U(24, 28))
4	Left surface position of RPV (cm)	(U(36, 44))
5	Right surface position of RPV (cm)	(U(56, 64))
6	Right surface position of cavity (cm)	(U(80, 100))
7	Water density	(U(0.7, 1.0))
8	Aluminum plate density	(U(2.6, 2.8))
9	Thermal shield density	(U(7.5, 8.5))
10	RPV density	(U(7.7, 8.0))
11	Cavity density	(U(0.00120, 0.00121))

3.2. Predictive Performance of the POD-ROM

The predictive accuracy of the proposed POD-ROM was assessed using an independent test set and benchmarked against high-fidelity RMC transport simulations. The reference solutions were generated with sufficient statistical precision, with relative error (RE) below 1% in the core, within 5% across the RPV, and about 5% in the cavity. As shown in Fig. 2, the ROM agrees closely with the RMC profiles over the full radial domain. For representative cases, R^2 is close to 1.0, while RMSE remains on the order of 10^{-3} ; the mean relative error ranges from $\sim 2\%$ to $\sim 12\%$.

Figure 2. Comparison between predicted flux of test samples and RMC simulation results

Figure 3. (a) Distribution of relative errors in the test set predictions; (b) Evaluation of prediction accuracy at various spatial locations

Figure 4 presents a representative comparison between the ROM prediction and the RMC transport solution. For identical inputs, a single RMC run takes about 20,580 s on average, whereas the POD-ROM evaluates in ~ 0.8 s, corresponding to a 5–6 orders of magnitude speedup. The resulting mean relative error is 5.75%, indicating that the ROM retains good generalization accuracy while delivering substantial computational savings.

Figure 4. Comparison between model predictions and RMC transport results for a representative input case

4. APPLICATION OF THE SHEW METHOD IN A 1-D PWR SHIELDING MODEL

4.1. Entropy-driven Importance Distribution and WW Generation

The POD-ROM enables rapid evaluation of response distributions under localized perturbations of regional parameters. Shannon entropy gain and KL divergence are computed for the perturbed responses to quantify each region’s contribution to tally uncertainty, which is then normalized into a radial importance distribution. As shown in Fig. 5(a), entropy increments increase markedly near material interfaces and transitions involving absorbing media, suggesting that perturbations in these zones have a disproportionate impact on response uncertainty.

To evaluate variance-reduction performance, the figure of merit (FOM) is used:

$$FOM = \frac{1}{R^2 T} \quad (16)$$

where R is the relative error of the cavity flux tally and T is the total CPU time (core-hours). SHEW method aims to maximize the FOM by allocating computational effort to regions with higher information gain.

On the basis of the normalized importance distribution, SHEW maps the importance to radial WW lower bounds. Figure 5(b) shows the resulting WW profile: high-importance regions are assigned smaller lower bounds to promote splitting and increase sampling, whereas low-importance regions receive larger bounds to suppress low-value histories, yielding an efficient and physically interpretable importance-control strategy for deep-penetration transport.

Figure 5. Entropy gain response and WW mapping in the cavity region: (a) distribution of induced entropy gain; (b) radial WW lower-bound profiles.

For the mesh tally at $x = 75$ cm in the cavity, Figure 6 presents the spatial information distribution and the resulting WW settings. The radial WW lower-bound profile is seen to be consistent with the underlying entropy distribution, providing a physically interpretable importance input for subsequent deep-penetration acceleration in RMC.

Fig. 6. Spatial information distribution for the mesh tally at $x = 75$ cm

4.2. Performance Comparison of Variance-reduction Schemes

After generating the entropy-driven weight window, it is written into an RMC-compatible WWP card and applied in fixed-source transport simulations of the 1-D PWR shielding model. The VR schemes considered for comparison include a traditional power-law cell-importance distribution [14] (with an adjacent-cell importance ratio of 4) and the SHEW-based automatically generated mesh weight window. Both schemes are executed under identical tally requirements and particle-history settings to ensure a fair comparison.

Figure 7 compares the cavity flux obtained with the two VR methods. When the number of histories is substantially reduced, the entropy-driven WW remains in good agreement with the high-precision reference, whereas the power-law cell-importance scheme shows noticeable bias in the deep-penetration cavity region, consistent with insufficient sampling.

Fig. 7. Comparison of RMC transport results with different variance-reduction methods

Table II summarizes CPU time and FOM. For 10^4 histories, the SHEW-based scheme achieves an FOM of 95.96, approximately nine times that of the cell-importance method (10.23), despite a modest increase in runtime. Overall, the results indicate that SHEW improves the amount of effective statistical information per unit computational cost and provides more robust convergence in strongly attenuated regions.

Table II. Comparison of CPU time and FOM for different variance-reduction schemes

Scheme	Histories	CPU time (core·h)	FOM
Cell importance (imp_Flux_1E4)	(1×10^4)	0.0539	10.2294
Entropy-driven WW (SHEW_Flux_1E4)	(1×10^4)	0.1170	95.9647
Cell importance (imp_Flux_1E6)	(1×10^6)	4.1318	37.6478

In summary, the 1-D PWR shielding case demonstrates that the POD-ROM and SHEW framework improves variance-reduction efficiency and FOM while preserving accurate cavity-flux predictions, highlighting its practical potential for deep-penetration ex-vessel shielding analyses.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a variance-reduction framework coupling a physics-constrained POD-ROM with the SHEW method was implemented within the RMC code. Evaluated through a representative PWR ex-vessel deep-penetration shielding problem, the POD-ROM demonstrated high predictive fidelity, achieving an $R^2 \approx 1.0$ and a mean relative error of approximately 5% while providing a speedup of 5–6 orders of magnitude over full-order transport calculations. Numerical results further confirmed that the SHEW method, which quantifies importance through an information-theoretic metric combining Shannon entropy and KL divergence, increases the FOM by approximately one order of magnitude compared to traditional power-law schemes. Overall, the proposed framework enables physically interpretable WW quantification and a rapid setup procedure for PWR ex-vessel shielding, offering a practical route toward more efficient MC simulations in engineering applications.

Despite the efficiency demonstrated in this study, the current 1-D framework serves primarily as a proof-of-concept for the entropy-driven WW methodology. The 1-D approximation inherently simplifies the complex angular flux anisotropy and transverse leakage effects present in realistic reactor configurations, which are critical for determining WW quality in multi-dimensional deep-penetration scenarios.

Future research will focus on extending the POD-based reduced-order framework to 3-D benchmarks to assess its robustness in complex geometries. Key areas include developing multidimensional

importance measures to guide the coordinated specification of 3-D WW meshes and integrating adaptive machine-learning techniques into RMC. These advancements aim to further enhance the engineering efficiency and physical interpretability of deep-penetration MC calculations.

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